

Exploring the impacts of international trade piracy on the oil and gas sector

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Abstract: The study's goal is to look into the effects of piracy on the oil and gas industry in Ghana. Oil exploration in Ghana began in the late 1800s with onshore drilling in the Tano Basin, which is now part of the Western Region, during British colonial authority. Piracy and robbery at sea, are anticipated to rise to an alarming degree in the Gulf of Guinea (GoG) region (IMB, 2018), exceeding that in Africa's Horn. The crews of ships, cargo, and other valuables are frequently the targets of these pirates and robbers. Since 2007, piracy (including armed robbery at sea) has increased at an alarming rate in the Gulf of Guinea (GoG), with incidents reaching a fourth of all documented incidents worldwide. Ghana, like every other country in the Gulf of Guinea (GoG), is facing rising marine security and safety issues, the most visible of which is piracy (Dalaklis, 2012). The impact on operations' environment related to the production of oil (oil contamination), unlawful dumping, and unlawful releases from ships has been identified as a major hazard in Ghana's oil and gas sector, and it requires immediate attention. Inadvertent releases into the sea, oil spills into the sea, and the process of oil spills are all examples of environmental pollution caused by oil exploration and drilling. Finally, toxic waste disposal must be factored into the overall environmental protection calculation. The study's goal identify elements assisting gas and oil piracy in Ghana, examine the impact of piracy on the oil and gas industry, examine the impact of piracy on the cost of oil shipping and insurance, and examine the impact of piracy's economic impact on gas and oil in Ghana. The study concentrates on descriptive research. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies. A total of 150 working staff in the gas and oil businesses in Ghana were chosen as a sample. The researcher used convenience sampling and purposive sampling as non-probability methodologies. A questionnaire was used to collect data as the study instrument. The Statistical Package for Social Scientists was used to analyze the data. According to the data collected and analyzed, the majority of respondents are men. When asked what causes facilitate oil and gas piracy, the respondents' majority agreed on legal (court adjudication on gas and oil disputes) and geographical (climate change) aspects, as well as pitifully low incomes, environmental suffering, and poverty. The respondents' majority agreed that consistent increases in commodity prices, costs of security incurred in the fight against piracy, and commercial activities' income being undermined were contributing gas and oil piracy factors when asked about the piracy's economic influence on gas and oil. The theft occurs as a result of piracy in the port area; some crew members are abducted while others are killed, and the hijacking may indicate a shift in the pirates' objectives and ambitions. Premiums and coverage are affected by the rise in pirate assaults, and war risk insurance must be purchased by ships to mitigate the impact of piracy on the cost of oil shipping and insurance.

Keywords: Oil and Gas, Security, risk

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Introduction

Research motivation

Piracy in the Minoan Mycenaean world dates back to the second millennium (Zohourian, 2020). Armed robbery and piracy have put the maritime safety of several countries at risk (Zohourian, 2020). Piracy attacks (comprising sea robbery) have increased at an unprecedented rate in the Gulf of Guinea (GoG) area since 2007, with incidents surpassing a quarter of all registered incidents worldwide (McCook, 2020). The daily shipment of nearly 5,000,000 tons of oil is hampered by maritime instability, which accounts for approximately 30% of US oil imports and more than half of total daily supply on Africa's west coast (Vircoulon and Tournier, 2014). Latest oil and gas discoveries off Africa's eastern seaboard pose new prospects and obstacles for countries and companies looking to tap the potential hydrocarbon deposits (Shepard and Pratson, 2020). Following the 1957 independence of Ghana, successive governments of the country looked into the hydrocarbon reserves of the country in order to diversify the country's riches and boost growth. Many oil organizations regard Ghana as a high-risk alternative for exploration of gas and oil due to high production costs and a hostile market climate caused by unlawful government policies in the past.

Thus, major changes in the way in which oil production is conducted have arisen since the return of the country to constitutional rule in 1992. Oil discovery in Ghana began in the late 19th century, with onshore exploration commenced under British colonial rule in the Western Region (then, the Tano Basin), today's Western Region. From 1896 to 1957, over 17 wells were drilled. Although some deposits of gas, light oil, and heavy oil were discovered, the reserves were in non-commercially viable amounts (GNPC, 2019). Successive post-independence governments, eager to find oil in Ghana, proceeded with onshore and offshore oil exploration. Around 75 oil wells were drilled from the First Republic of Kwame Nkrumah (1957–1966) to the Fourth Republic of John Agyekum Kufuor (2000–2008) (Tullow Oil Plc, 2013). The Gulf of Guinea is a very active shipping lane that joins a large number of nations while also providing a considerable source of money for countries refining oil along its coast (Nwokedi et al., 2020). With 17 coastal nations and two island nations along the shores of central and western Africa, it is located partially in the South and North Atlantic Oceans (Nwokedi et al., 2020). In 2007, huge gas and oil discoveries in the Jubilee field reawakened Ghanaians' hopes that Ghana was to become an oil producer.

The Jubilee field is around 60 kilometers off Ghana's Western Region coast, near Cape Three Points. Tullow Ghana Limited manages the Jubilee field, owned by Jubilee Joint Venture (a group of firms). The Jubilee unit area is expected to have a gross resource base ranging from 500,000,000 oil barrels (P90) (mmbo) to 700 (P50) mmbo, with a potential advantage of 1000 (P10) mmbo. Between 1.5 billion and 800 million oil barrels are estimated to be in the reserve (Sunu-Attah, 2017). But, Ghana, like every other Gulf of Guinea (GoG) region, faces rising maritime security and security challenges, including piracy (Dalaklis, 2012). Piracy and stealing at sea are, however, expected to increase at an unprecedented pace in the GoG area (IMB, 2018), exceeding those in the Horn of Africa (Nwokedi et al., 2020). These robbers and pirates typically attack other valuables, freight, and crew members of the ship (ICC International Maritime Bureau, 2021).

In the zone of GoG, in the maritime realms of Nigeria (1 hijacked), Benin (2 hijacked), and Ghana (1 hijacked), a series of 22 piracy attacks occurred in the first quarter of 2018, with very high rates of success (IMB, 2018). In the first quarter of 2018, the number of accidents exceeded that of all other countries. As part of this broader picture, the Transocean Logistics and Shipping assault can be identified in most parts of the globe. The Disguised Brigade, an Al Qaeda offshoot,

was liable for the strike at Transocean Logistics and Shipping (Nwokedi et al., 2020). One important figure of the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) Al-Qaeda group was Mokhtar Belmokhtar, the chief of the group, but Belmokhtar was deprived of his title because of infighting (Schneider and Schneider, 2020). As said by Joscelyn and Roggio (2013), in late 2012, he and his soldiers deserted AQIM and created the Masked Brigade, which now reports to the senior leadership of Al Qaeda.

Moreover, the key threats often found in Ghana's sector of gas and oil are the environmental effects of the activities related to the processing of oil (oil pollution), the illegal discharge of ships, and the illegal dumping of ships, which are enormous, and the requisite attention must be paid. Environmental contamination from oil exploration and drilling is primarily in the method of spillage oil into the sea, the process of unintentional oil spills, and unintentional releases into the sea (Nwalozie, 2020). Also, the full environmental mitigation calculation would incorporate the dumping of hazardous waste into its entirety. Furthermore, the illicit bunkering/crude oil smuggling in Ghana was also the gas and oil industry's problem. Illegal bunkering entails the acquisition, often at reduced prices, of unlawfully obtained or refined oil goods. It is usually obtained with unlawful intent for mischief or personal gain from the oil pipelines' vandalism and stolen oil (Nwalozie, 2020). Manufactured materials and crude diversion by illegal people at sea is also a concern. Illegal bunkering continues to boost crime activity. For example, armed robbery and piracy at sea increase when firms continue to patronize these inexpensive goods (Akah and Dalaklis, 2017).

In view of this history, the Ghanaian Navy detained MT Metrix 1 and MT Mammy Mary on April 14, 2018 when they illegally exchanged oil shipments of around 5 NM from Tema Harbour (Ocloo, 2018). As a result, a variety of policy-level efforts by the regional member states to adopt a Strategic Plan for the Maritime Environment's Security and Protection in Central and West Africa have been conducted to resolve the situation. Of special concern to Ghana was the operationalization of the Information System for Vessel Traffic Monitoring (VTMIS). Eight remote sensor sites are situated alongside Ghana's coast, from eastern Togo to western Cote d'Ivoire (GMA, 2014), with every relevant infrastructure. They are the key components of VTMIS in Ghana. However, the study sought to examine how international trade piracy impacts the oil and gas sector in Ghana.

As stated by the ICC International Maritime Bureau (2021) report, piracy at sea is an issue that occurs in countries around the world. In 2021, countries in Asia, America, and Africa experienced thirty-three (33) boarded attacks, 1 hijacked attack, 2 attempted attacks, and fired upon attempted attacks. However, Ghana has experienced two actual board attacks from January to March 2021, which have affected the economy of Ghana. Moreover, the impact of piracy attacks on the oil and gas sector in Ghana has not been explored. As a result, the study sought to examine how international trade piracy impacts the oil and gas sector in Ghana. Studies indicate that there are deficiencies in evidence on the impacts of international trade piracy on the gas and oil sectors in Ghana (Zohourian, 2020; McCook, 2020; Shepard and Pratson, 2020; Nwokedi et al., 2020; Nwalozie, 2020). To begin with, it should be mentioned that no such comprehensive studies of Ghanaian organizations have been undertaken (Shepard and Pratson, 2020). Second, the research was limited to distinct geographical and cultural contexts, making it impossible to generalize the findings (Nwalozie, 2020; McCook, 2020). Thirdly, there are no studies on transocean sea trade in Ghana. Therefore, it is on this premise that this study sought to examine the impact of international trade piracy on the oil and gas sector in Ghana.

Research Questions

The research questions to be addressed in the study are: (1) What are the elements assisting gas and oil piracy in Ghana? (2) What is the impact of piracy on the gas and oil industry? (3) What is the impact of piracy on the cost of oil shipping and insurance? (4) What is the economic impact of piracy on gas and oil in Ghana?

Research objectives

The aim of the study is to explore the impacts of international trade piracy on the oil and gas sector in Ghana. To assist in the realization of the general objective, the following specific objectives are developed as: (1) Identifying elements that aid gas and oil piracy in Ghana. (2) To examine the impact of piracy on the gas and oil industries. (3) To examine the impact of piracy on the cost of oil shipping and insurance. (4) To examine the impact of piracy's economic impact on gas and oil in Ghana.

Research Contribution

Descriptive research was the study concentration. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies. A total of 150 working staff in Delta State from gas and oil businesses were chosen as a sample. Because it was more convenient, the researcher used purposive and convenience sampling as a non-probability sampling method. The methods used involve administering surveys to members of the oil and gas industry's management and workers in Takoradi, Cape Three Points. The researcher then used the Statistical Package for Social Scientists to evaluate the primary data and ensure that it was accurate. The survey contributes to literature since the survey method confirms survey methods used in literature.

The report discusses elements assisting gas and oil piracy in Ghana. Also discussed is the impact of piracy on the oil and gas industry. And moreover, the impact of piracy on the cost of oil shipping and insurance. The report further discusses the economic effect on the gas and oil sectors. This research production will add to the information and literature on the topic under review. Furthermore, the study will be relevant to international bodies who have an interest in international trade piracy and oil and gas business. So, the study will inform them on the situation in Ghana. The results of the study will inform the trade and industry ministry, energy ministry and Ghana government on issues relating to international trade piracy in Ghana's gas and oil sector. This study will inform other stakeholders and policymakers on international trade piracy in Ghana's gas and oil sectors. It would also act as a helpful reference for the management and workers of the gas and oil industries. The study will contribute to the literature since no studies on international trade piracy in the gas and oil sectors have been conducted in Ghana. Lastly, the results of the study will guide students and researchers who will explore studies relating to international trade piracy and the oil and gas sector.

Literature Review

Impact of piracy on economic development

Below are the empirical studies on piracy's impact on economic development by various researchers;

Has the die been cast for an environmental calamity, according to Herbig and Fouché's (2013) study on maritime piracy and conservation crime in Africa? To map actual recent accidents and make forecasts, the researchers used secondary data from credible global organizations accountable for many elements of maritime safety. This study aims to contextualize and uncover the crime conservation threat posed by piracy in order to serve as a warning to practitioners and policymakers about this looming threat and to pique additional interest, research, and investigation into the subject. Ikelegbe (2005) did a study on the economic conflict in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria's Oil-Rich. The study looks at the economics of violence in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria's resource conflicts. Since the 1990s, a conflict economy

has emerged, characterized by intense and violent competition for resource possibilities, intra-and inter-ethnic/communal conflicts over resources, and the trade and theft of crude and refined oil. The research investigates the economic interactions between the Nigerian government, multinational oil firms, the international community, and youth militias. Although the economy did not create the conflict, it was discovered that it had become a part of the resistance and a resource for maintaining it. The economy is at the root of the widespread expansion of guns and violent institutions, as well as the pervasiveness of crime, violence, and communal/ethnic conflict.

Briggs (2017) published a report titled "Maritime Piracy: "Global Oil Transportation Security Disruptive Implications." Terrorist attacks can cause damage and disruption to the crude oil delivery network. However, they are rare. Terrorists have targeted the petroleum industry in the past. Large amounts of crude oil freight are transported around the world, and the manner and route of transport, as well as general security management, are not always optimal. According to the findings, increased alertness, watch keeping, and other protective measures have significantly increased the odds of stopping terrorist and pirate assaults at sea. Indeed, the findings of this study strongly suggest that implementing some of the International Maritime Bureau's suggested ship protective measures to combat piracy has been shown to be beneficial to some extent. Because the globe's economic survival depends on a steady supply of petroleum products, it's critical to protect this industry from security threats all around the world.

Alon et al. (2006) examine the industry-precise risks associated with the sectors of gas and oil, arguing that they are one of the riskiest areas to invest in (2006). They are backed up by Moran (2011), who claims that since the involved resources are frequently regarded as a nation's national patrimony, investments in this sector are likely to have a greater impact on the country than other investments (because of the power and wealth that come with oil production). Agyare-Asiamah (2019) did a study to investigate the awareness issue of the maritime domain in Ghana. The goal was to look at Ghana's MDA abilities, determine present operational and technical ability, and identify the main issues that limit effective collaboration between those agencies, as well as potential solutions. The study endeavor also identified the actions/initiatives that enforcement of law agencies in the nation under consideration should take to conduct improvement in security operations or/and maritime safety. Finally, it is critical to improve the maritime security capacity of Ghana by properly utilizing the present MDA tools in the maritime of Ghana's associated agencies and performance optimization by creating a framework of standard operating procedures and special cooperation that are appropriate for every pertinent stakeholder.

Maritime piracy and conservation crime in Africa were investigated by Herbig and Founche (2019). To map actual recent accidents and make projections, the authors used secondary data from credible global organizations accountable for many elements of maritime safety. This study aims to contextualize and uncover the crime conservation threat posed by piracy in order to serve as a warning to practitioners and policymakers about this looming threat and to pique additional interest, research, and investigation into the subject. Coggins (2012) did a study on global patterns of maritime piracy. Over the same decade, there were a total of 1,470 sightings of pirate episodes originating from the world's one hundred and forty-seven coastline nations. Entries include data on the maritime sector at the national level, such as shipping coastal traffic, seaports, coastline length, marine merchant size, and distances to important chokepoints in sea lanes. The paper outlines the data's primary characteristics, offers descriptive statistics, and concisely highlights their research utility. Scholars investigating non-traditional threats posed by non-state actors, as well as those investigating the possible links between conflict and governance on piracy at sea and on land, may find the MPD useful,

as may those conducting policy-relevant analyses evaluating the efficiency and effectiveness of counter-piracy tactics and strategies.

A study conducted by Thadeus (2013) on the effect of Somali piracy on Kenya's maritime sector. The study sampled Kenya Maritime officials, clearing agents, shipping agents, Kenya Revenue Authority officials, and hotel industry officials on the Coast. The study achieved its purpose through three objectives, namely: to establish the effect of Somali piracy on Kenya's import and export trade; to find out the effect of Somali piracy on the tourism sector on the Kenyan coast; and to determine the effects of Somali piracy on maritime security in Kenya. The data gathered was analyzed by a data analysis mixed method, including quantitative and qualitative methods. SPSS Version 17 was employed to analyze quantitative data. The study concludes that Somalia's piracy affects Kenya's import/export, the tourism industry, and maritime security. The study recommends that at the national governmental level, the government must discover means to raise awareness and enhance enforcement of piracy issues. Zohourian (2020) evaluated the data about armed robberies and piracy of ships provided to the Integrated Global Shipping System of Information. The statistics include data on events involving various types of ships in two of the world's most vital areas: the Malacca Strait (area 1) and the South China Sea (SCS), and the Persian Gulf (area 2) and the Hormuz Strait. In contrast to the Malacca Strait, Zohourian (2020) shows that attacks on port areas were more common in the China South Sea. McCook (2020) is involved in a qualitative, comparative most-similar-systems case study of Angola and Nigeria to examine an unexamined, previously variable role: the extent to which patronage structures and management strategies of elite rent inhibit or foster an environment permissive wherein piracy can flourish. McCook (2020) contends that decentralized management practices of rent intensify piracy incentives in Nigeria, whereas centralized high-rent management discourages Angola piracy. These findings suggest that piracy levels will stay low in Angola and high in Nigeria.

Shepard and Pratson (2020) investigate maritime piracy's impact on various fuel exports from each PGC via this chokepoint. They characterize piracy in the Strait of Malacca as a "soft limitation." The impact of such a limitation is dependent on the trading countries' risk aversion and the type of petroleum exchanged. They utilize a least-squares two-stage regression to first assess the impact of piracy attacks on traffic tankers across the Strait of Malacca and then to assess the risk of energy exports being harmed as a result of the restriction. The first stage of the investigation showed that two years following piracy assaults, tanker transit dropped.

However, the second step of the research shows that only Bahraini and Kuwaiti refined petroleum exports are seriously impacted. Shepard and Pratson (2020) discovered that soft limitations in the form of piracy had minimal long-term impact on exports of energy from most of the PGC.

Piracy increases cost

The Nave Constellation supertanker was kidnapped in early December. About seventy-seven nautical miles (143 kilometers) from Bonny Island, Nigeria's Rivers State loading terminal, pirates boarded the loaded ship, abducted nineteen crew members, and stole its oil cargo (Al Jazeera News, 2019). While supertanker attacks are uncommon, piracy is so widespread in the Gulf of Guinea that the International Maritime Bureau (IMB) called it "one of the world's most dangerous maritime routes" and a "global piracy hotspot" in a July report. Nonetheless, since it is such an important component of the provincial economy, ships continue to navigate its waterways and bear the rising costs associated with the maritime piracy threat. As said by the Danish Foreign Affairs Ministry, 90% of trade to West Africa is carried out by sea, making maritime security a critical aspect of the province's economy. According to IMB data,

pirates abducted twenty-seven crew members in the first half of 2019, and one out of every four international piracy occurrences in 2018 occurred in the territorial seas of Nigeria, as stated by Global Allianz (Al Jazeera News, 2019). Piracy thrives in these situations. The Gulf of Guinea runs from Angola to Senegal, covering 4,247 square miles (11,000 square kilometers).

It is one of the most significant shipping routes in the world for consumer products from and to West and Central Africa and oil shipments from the Niger Delta, yet it is poorly secured, creating ideal piracy conditions. "Congestion at Lagos ports and the lack of other options means that ships are spending a long time queuing, meaning there are a large number of ships in a relatively small area to target," said Peccavi Consulting security firm, UK-based Chidi Nwaonu (Al Jazeera News, 2019). Due to that and a lack of naval presence, "there is the motive of high financial reward and a comparatively low risk of detection or capture." In March, thirty-three nations gathered in the Gulf to conduct marine security training, with several speakers emphasizing the necessity for increased infrastructure, cooperation, and funding (Al Jazeera News, 2019). In an effort to combat an increase in pirate attacks, the navy of Nigeria has placed eight automated, camera-equipped observation towers in the waters close off its shore. [Reuters/Stringer/File] State governments in the federal system of Nigeria have very rudimentary capacity to combat piracy and should rely on the federal government to police the waters. Nigeria does not currently have a plan to deal with this threat, "SBM Intelligence research head, Cheta Nwanze, a Lagos-based political analysis and security business, told Al Jazeera.

Nwaonu agreed. Nigeria's navy is the most powerful in the GoG (Gulf of Guinea), but compared to the army and air force, it has been underfunded and neglected. Kidnappings at sea have become so regular, according to industry experts, that they have raised the operational cost. Companies must budget for security, independent contractors, ransom money, and additional insurance (Al Jazeera News, 2019). Everything adds up. Piracy cost West Africa \$818.1 million in 2017, up from \$793.7 million the year before. As stated by the NGO Oceans Beyond Piracy's 2017 State of Marine Piracy report, about a fifth of the \$818.1 million was spent on maritime security contracts. Insurance is likewise very expensive. According to Oceans Beyond Piracy's analysis, the total cost of increased war area risk premiums ships incurred traversing the Gulf in 2017 was \$18.5 million, with 35% of ships carrying ransom insurance and additional kidnap totaling \$20.7 million. Because of the high level of insecurity in the region, global insurance giant Beazley has created "Gulf of Guinea Piracy Plus," a specialized insurance plan for maritime crews passing through (Al Jazeera News, 2019). Even in ransom demands' absence, the plan guarantees recompense for personnel kidnappings and unlawful vessel seizures. It monitors insured vessels 24 hours a day, but claims are limited to \$15 million due to the high danger. Premiums for this coverage type, however, are determined case-by-case, according to a Beazley spokeswoman, because the dangers are so considerable. The situation came to a head in June 2019, when the Shipping Directorate General of India announced a ban on every Indian citizen working in the maritime industry in the Gulf of Guinea and Nigeria (Al Jazeera News, 2019). The fact that India would impose such a restriction emphasizes the problem's severity, as Indians compose one of the region's largest sailor contingents. Nigeria is the second-largest contributor of sailors to the international marine fleet after the Philippines and is Nigeria's largest trading partner for its oil exports, explained Nwanze (Al Jazeera News, 2019). Whereas the ban is one of the region's strongest acknowledgements of piracy maritime, it does not seem to be sufficient of a deterrent for Indian citizens seeking jobs on such a worthwhile route of shipping. Five Indian sailors were saved from a ship hijacked a few weeks after the embargo started (Al Jazeera News, 2019). Except for one, the kidnapped sailors on the Nave Constellation were all Indian. The crewmen were freed 3 weeks after

hijacking the supertanker, according to a released joint statement by the vessel's owner, Maritime Acquisition of Navios Corporation, and manager, Tanker Management of Anglo-Eastern. "Since the attack, the prime concern has been the safety, well-being, and early return of the seafarers taken by the pirate gang. "Owners and managers are now delighted to report that on December 21, all of those taken were released and are now safe and undergoing medical tests and debriefing, following which they will return to their loved ones at home," the statement read (Al Jazeera News, 2019). Despite this, the firms declined to confirm or provide kidnapping operational details because maritime piracy risks were so high.

Analysis and Discussions of Results

This chapter entails responses interpretation from interviews and administered questionnaires, analysis, results presentation, and detailed information about political piracy in the gas and oil data from the study.

Analysis and Data Presentation

Tables and graphs were used to present participant's responses.

Respondents' Social-Demographics Characteristics

Respondents' Gender

Table 1: Respondents' Gender

	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
MALE	87	58	58
FEMALE	63	42	100
TOTAL	150	100	

Source: Field Work, 2021

In Table 1, sixty-three (63) participants, representing 42%, are female, whereas eighty-seven (87) participants, representing 58%, are male. This shows that male participation was greater than female participation, as shown in Figure 1.

Respondents' Age group

Table 2: Respondents' Age group

	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
20-30 years	56	37	37
31-40 years	41	27	64
41-50 years	29	19	83
>50 years	24	16	100
TOTAL	150	100	

In Table 5, fifty-six (56) participants are 20 years, 30 years or between, representing 37%. Forty-one (41) participants are 31 years, 40 years, or somewhere in between, signifying 27%. Twenty-nine (29) participants are 41 years old, 50 years old, or in between, signifying 19%. Twenty-four (24) participants are over 50, signifying 16%. This result shows that most participants are at their youthful working age of 20, 30, or between as shown in Figure 2.

Work experience in the gas and oil Company

Table 3: Work experience in the company

	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
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1-5 years	30	20	20
6-10 years	37	25	45
11-15 years	35	23	68
16-20 years	26	17	85
21 years and more	22	15	100
TOTAL	150	100	

Source: Field Work, 2021

In Figure 3 and Table 6, thirty-seven (37) employees of the Transocean Sea trade, signifying 25%, had 6–10 years of work experience. Thirty-five (35) respondents, representing 23%, had 11–15 years’ work experience. Thirty (30) respondents, or 20%, had one to five years of work experience. Twenty-six (26) indicating 17% had 16–20 years’ work experience and twenty-two (22) indicating 15% had more than 21 years’ work experience. This shows that most participants had 6–10 years of work experience.

Respondents’ Qualification

Table 4: Respondents’ Qualification

	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative (%)
SHS	22	15	15
Diploma	48	32	47
Undergraduate	46	31	78
Postgraduate	34	23	100
TOTAL	150	100	

Source: Field Work, 2021

In Table 7, twenty-two (22) participants, representing 15%, hold senior high school certificates. Forty-eight (48) participants hold a diploma certificate, signifying 32%. Forty-six (46) hold undergraduate certificates, representing 31%. Thirty-four (34) participants, representing 23%, obtained postgraduate certificates. This shows that most participants are educated.

Occurrence of Oil and Gas Piracy

When asked how frequently they hear about oil and gas piracy in Ghana, respondents said it was quite frequently. On a five-ordered scale, the dominant nodes are highly predominant, highly predominant, predominant, seldom predominant, and non-predominant. The results obtained from the respondents are represented in the figure below.

Figure 1: Oil and Gas Piracy Predominance Source: Field Work, 2021

According to Figure 1, 62 (41%) of respondents saw oil and gas piracy as highly prevalent in Ghana, as shown in red, 48 (32%) saw it as predominant, which is the moderate as shown in yellow, 29 (19%) saw it as highly prevalent as shown in green, 7 (5%) saw it as rarely predominant as shown in blue, and the remaining 4 (3%) saw oil and gas piracy as not prevalent.

Elements assisting gas and oil piracy in Ghana

Table 5: Elements assisting gas and oil piracy

RESPONSES	Frequency Analysis					Average	Category
	1	2	3	4	5	Index	of Rating
1=Strongly agree, 2=Agree, 3= Neutral, 4= Disagree, 5= Strongly disagree	No. of Respondents						Scale
A	29	56	20	30	15	2.64	3
B	37	48	17	35	13	2.49	2
C	39	43	16	23	29	2.73	3
D	21	63	19	26	21	2.75	3
E	14	31	21	56	28	3.35	3
F	34	51	19	36	10	2.45	2
G	22	33	15	45	35	3.25	3
H	36	39	24	31	20	2.13	2
I	29	58	10	31	22	2.73	3
J	21	68	11	27	23	2.75	3
K	36	49	16	36	13	2.61	3
L	43	78	2	20	7	2.73	3

Source: Field Work, 2021

Table 5 displays responses for the elements assisting gas and oil piracy to answer the first research question. The majority of participants disagreed that maritime and pastoralist resources’ reduction because of illegal fishing and drought (IND = 3.25) and low risks for capture (IND = 3.35) are the contributive elements for gas and oil piracy. A majority of participants agreed that pitifully low incomes (IND = 2.75) and legal (judicial adjudication on gas and oil cases) and geographical (for example, climate change) environment (IND = 2.75), poverty (IND = 2.73), and environmental hardship (IND = 2.73) are the elements supporting gas and oil piracy (IND = 2.73).

Conclusion and Implications

Summary of the findings

The research sought to examine piracy's impacts on the gas and oil sectors using a case study of Transocean Sea Trade. To find elements assisting gas and oil piracy in Takoradi’s Transocean Sea Trade (cape three point) was the key purpose. The gathered and analyzed data showed that male participation was higher than female participation. Most participants

were at their youthful working age of 20, 30, or between. Most participants had 6–10 years of work experience. Most participants were educated. On the question of elements assisting gas and oil piracy, the study found that:

- Most of the participants disagreed that maritime and pastoralist resources are being reduced because of illegal fishing and drought.
- Low capture risks were a contributing factor for gas and oil.
- They also agreed that pitifully low incomes, legal (judicial adjudication on gas and oil cases), and geographical (for example, climate change), environment, poverty, and environmental hardship were the elements supporting gas and oil piracy.

Moreover, on the question of piracy's economic impact on gas and oil, the study found that

- A majority of participants disagreed that scaled-down investors were the contributive element of Lagos' gas and oil
- They likewise agreed that a consistent increase in commodity prices, in the fight against piracy, security costs incurred, and commercial activities' income being undermined were gas and oil piracy's contributive elements.

Also, on the question of the impact of piracy on Ghana's oil and gas industry, the results revealed that

- When pirate ships go aground, sink, or catch fire, they cause tremendous environmental harm.
- Piracy has an effect on the cost of shipping imported raw materials and oil.
- Piracy has caused a reduction in oil production, costing the Ghanaian economy millions of dollars.
- Maritime piracy poses a threat to energy security, which is a worry.
- The hijacking could signal a shift in the pirates' objectives and ambitions.
- Piracy forces oil and gas corporations to take a different, substantially longer and more expensive route.
- The cost of carrying imported raw materials and oil is affected by the route of a single tanker.
- Pirates attack a ship carrying tons of diesel fuel.
- Some members of the crew are abducted, while others are slain.

Lastly, on the question of the impact of piracy on the cost of oil shipping and insurance, the study found that

- Premiums and coverage are affected by the rise in pirate assaults.
- War risk insurance must be purchased by ships.
- The cost of shipping insurance is increasing.
- Kidnap and ransom insurance premiums are rising.
- Piracy-related costs are passed on to customers because shipping businesses recoup the majority of their losses through protection and indemnity agreements.
- Higher insurance premiums are factored into shipper pricing.

Conclusion

This study's purpose was to examine piracy's impact on the gas and oil sectors. Gas and oil piracy highlight the modern and important roles that non-state actors play in global, regional, and national political economies. Today's transnational security threat qualities are combined by piracy: private actors, who can possibly collaborate with terrorists, involved in asymmetry attacks, legal and globalization grey spheres' profit, and other main challenges of transnational society, for example, organized crime, ecological degradation, and climate-change. A more complete definition of piracy is

needed, because transocean trade meaning bounds piracy to illegal actions of incarceration or coercion performed on the high seas, excluding similar actions performed in a state's littoral waters. The theft occurs as a result of piracy in the port area; some crew members are abducted while others are killed, and the hijacking may indicate a shift in the pirates' objectives and ambitions. Premiums and coverage are affected by the rise in pirate assaults, and war risk insurance must be purchased by ships to mitigate the impact of piracy on the cost of oil shipping and insurance.

Policy Implications

Based on conclusions drawn and findings, recommendations for stakeholders were made as follows: International, sub-regional, and inter-agency stakeholders must work together to build a comprehensive legal system that covers everything from issue description to crime adjudication and punishment. All parties would be encouraged to participate without apprehensions or frustration if the legal framework for dealing with the pirate threat was transparent. Given the transnational nature of most challenges and vulnerabilities, an effective counter-piracy strategy for Transocean Trade Company in Tarkoradi (cape three point) necessitates consistency between domestic, regional, and international partner-related programs, as well as significant collaboration.

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